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Introduction

This project aims to function as a guide for scientists that are interested in working with analysis of lncRNAs (Long No Coding RNAs) and, to help with that, various bioinformatics tools (m6Anet oriented) and tutorials will be updated in this repository.

Prerequisites

- [WSL](#) or [Ubuntu](#) machine
- [Conda](#)

Step 0: Find Long No Coding RNAs within literature

The main objective of this tutorial is to help find differentially methylated DRACH motifs on long-no-coding RNAs related to SARS-CoV-2 infection. To do that, firstly, we recommend searching in the literature about genes that are LNC and seem to have significance in SARS-CoV-2 infection.

For further curation it is recommended to download and install [Geneious](#) in order to use the "map-to-reference" tool of your reads against the gene of interest.

Step 1: Obtain genes

In order to exemplify, firstly we will use the gene TUG1 available on: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/823>

Step 2: Install m6Anet

In order to install m6Anet, you can follow the instructions on their repository ([Goekelab/m6Anet](#)) or execute one of the following commands under a python environment:

```
Pip install m6anet
conda install m6anet
```

Step 3: Install Nanopolish

One of the prerequisites to run m6Anet is to install the Nanopolish tool, since it will be important to index the fastq files that will be obtained shortly after. Conda installation (Requires Conda managed environment)

```
conda install bioconda::nanopolish
```

Step 4: Install Samtools

Samtools will be important to manage the alignment (.bam) files, solving their respective indexes.

```
conda install bioconda::samtools
```

Step 5: Install minimap2

Minimap2 is needed to generate Binary Alignment Files (.bam).

```
conda install bioconda::minimap2
```

Step 6: Download Brute Fast5 Data from NCBI

To start analyzing the lncRNAs, it is crucial to have the brute Fast5 files from one of the NCBI SRA projects, in this particular example we will be using the project PRJNA608224, with the following SRAs:

- [Nanopore direct RNA sequencing of SARS-CoV-2:Calu control 48hpi \(SRR13089335\)](#) - Uninfected Calu-3 Cells
- [Nanopore direct RNA sequencing of SARS-CoV-2:Calu infected 48hpi \(SRR13089334\)](#) - Infected Calu-3 Cells

Step 7: Run Minimap2 map to reference Pipeline on gene TUG1 and Run Samtools index

In this particular example, we are using Calu_48_Control to be mapped against TUG1 gene.

```
minimap2 -a -x map-ont TUG1.fasta ../../Calu_48_Control.fastq.gz | samtools view -bS -F 4 | samtools sort > TUG1.sorted.bam && samtools index TUG1.sorted.bam
```

Step 8: Run nanopolish eventalign generating their respective directories

```
mkdir summary && mkdir eventalign && nanopolish eventalign --reads ../../Calu_48_Control.fastq.gz --bam TUG1.sorted.bam --genome TUG1.fasta --scale-events --signal-index --summary summary/summary.txt --threads 50 > eventalign/eventalign.txt
```

Step 9: Run m6Anet dataprep step

modify the "--n_processes" parameter according with your processor thread count

```
m6anet dataprep --eventalign eventalign/eventalign.txt --out_dir output/ --n_processes 12
```

Step 10: Run m6Anet Inference Step

```
m6anet inference --input_dir output/ --out_dir output_csv/
```

Step 11: Visualize Results

After Step 10, there will be two ".csv" files generated which will be useful for Further analysis. Those files should be in the following format:

"TUG1_control_data.site_proba.csv"

transcript_id	transcript_position	n_reads	probability_modified	kmer	mod_ratio
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8796	22	0.9778926968574524	GAACT	0.6818181818181818
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8567	20	0.8949198126792908	GGAAT	0.5000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8938	24	0.7990716099799075	AGACT	0.3333333333333333
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9043	22	0.7729524374080179	GGACA	0.2272727272727273
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8999	22	0.7173609733581543	GGACA	0.4090909090909091
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9032	22	0.7164373993873596	AGACT	0.4090909090909091
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8858	21	0.6472197175029540	TGACT	0.2857142857142857
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8274	20	0.6426706910133362	AAACT	0.2000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8590	20	0.6008827090263367	GGACC	0.1500000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9048	24	0.5542535185813904	GGACA	0.1666666666666667
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8693	22	0.4552282691001892	GAACC	0.0909090909090909
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8969	23	0.2691679894924164	AAACT	0.1304347826086956
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8945	24	0.0934556573629379	TGACC	0.0000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9052	23	0.0546207129985292	AAACT	0.0434782608695652
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9090	25	0.0025682873092592	TAACC	0.0000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8303	20	0.0001461697247578	TAACC	0.0000000000000000

."TUG1_infected_data.site_proba.csv"

transcript_id	transcript_position	n_reads	probability_modified	kmer	mod_ratio
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8567	20	0.9186328649520874	GGAAT	0.5500000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8922	24	0.8986399173736572	GGACA	0.4166666666666667
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8999	24	0.8736906647682190	GGACA	0.4583333333333333
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8938	26	0.7631926365600059	AGACT	0.3846153846153846
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8796	24	0.7217231392860413	GAACT	0.4583333333333333
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9032	22	0.6873892545700073	AGACT	0.4090909090909091
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9043	25	0.6554465293884277	GGACA	0.2800000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8693	22	0.6370372176170349	GAAAC	0.1363636363636364
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8858	24	0.6279472112655640	TGACT	0.2916666666666667
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8590	20	0.6028745174407959	GGACC	0.2000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8969	26	0.4058301746845245	AAACT	0.2307692307692308
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9052	24	0.0971080650820007	AAACT	0.0416666666666667
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9048	25	0.08669876519127	GAACA	0.0000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8945	24	0.0440216287970543	TGACC	0.0000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	8543	21	0.0107054673135281	TAACA	0.0000000000000000
NC_060946.1:31432823-31442955	9090	30	0.0029145909938961	TAACC	0.0000000000000000

Step 12: Analyzing Results

In order to compare the distribution of methylated sites per transcript in sequencing reads from uninfected and infected cells, we performed the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney (WMW) test, as implemented in R version 4.4.2 within the base R package. This nonparametric test is widely used to assess differences between two independent groups when their distributions do not meet the assumptions identical, whereas the alternative hypothesis (H_1) posits that the distributions differ significantly, specifically by detecting a difference in their medians.

To apply the WMW test to our data, we firstly gathered all predictions generated by m6Anet and stored them in tables, which were subsequently imported into R as data frames and labeled as "uninfected" and "infected". Then, a probability threshold was applied (modification probability ≥ 0.6) to filter out sites with low confidence in m6A modification.

The primary variable chosen to compare the methylation distribution between the two groups was the number of reads per site (n reads). Since the number of reads per site is not standardized by default, data normalization was required. For this, the number of reads per site in each group was divided by the total number of reads in that group using the equation expressed below. After normalization, the data underwent a negative logarithm

transformation (-log) to enhance visualization consistency across samples:

$$\frac{n_{reads}}{site} = \frac{n_{reads}}{\sum n_{reads}} \cdot \frac{site}{site}$$

To visualize the distributional differences between groups, we generated violin plots using the ggplot2 package (version 3.5.1) in R. Violin plots provide comprehensive graphical representation of data distribution by combining a box plot with a kernel density estimate, enabling the visualization of both summary statistics and the underlying probability density function. An example of violin plot is showed as below:

Step 13: IntaRNA interaction analysis

Explanation

IntaRNA is a powerful tool for predicting interactions between RNA molecules, such as lncRNAs and microRNAs (miRNAs).

IntaRNA calculates the hybridization energy between two RNA molecules to predict the most likely interaction site. The fundamental principle is that a more stable interaction has a lower Gibbs free energy (a more negative value). The tool not only predicts the total energy of the interaction but also considers the accessibility of the binding sites on both RNA molecules, which makes its prediction more accurate.

There are two ways to use IntaRNA, the first is through the web server hosted at [IntaRNA Server](#), offering a simpler (but limited on sequence length) workflow for predicting interactions between 2 molecules. The second way is to download and IntaRNA locally and, since we applied it locally, we covered the installation and configuration process below.

IntaRNA local installation

Conda Installation (Requires Conda managed environment):

```
conda install -c bioconda intarna
```

After installation, you can test IntaRNA by calling:

```
IntaRNA --version
```

It should output something like:

```
IntaRNA 3.4.1  
using Vienna RNA package 2.7.0 and boost 1.85.0
```

Usage

To start IntaRNA Interaction prediction, download two ".fasta" sequences of interest and run the following command, for example:

```
IntaRNA --query=./Seqs/[your_query_sequence].fasta
--target=./Seqs/[your_target].fasta --mode=H --outNumber=10 --outmode C --threads
12 > output.csv
```

Since intaRNA is a complex program, it may be appropriate to check the original software documentation, available on: <https://github.com/BackofenLab/IntaRNA>

Interaction Analysis

After running IntaRNA, the program should emit a ".csv" file, exemplified as the following image:

```
# INFO : Since no seed constraint needed: resetting model from 'X' to 'S'
```

id1	start1	end1	id2	start2	end2	subseqDP	hybridDP	E
ENST00000397381.4	1816	1904	NC_045512.2	513	600	CCCACCUUA	(((.....(((.....)))	-25.82
ENST00000397381.4	532	579	NC_045512.2	4253	4296	GUCUGACCC	(((.....(((.....)))	-24.15
ENST00000397381.4	1817	1904	NC_045512.2	513	599	CCACCUUAC	(((.....(((.....)))	-23.53
ENST00000397381.4	1812	1904	NC_045512.2	513	604	UUAACCCAC	((.....(((.....)))	-23.44
ENST00000397381.4	1813	1904	NC_045512.2	513	603	UAACCCAC	((.....(((.....)))	-22.88
ENST00000397381.4	540	579	NC_045512.2	4253	4289	CCUCAAACU	(((.....(((.....)))	-22.35

With the SubseqDP + hybridDP columns results, it is possible to visualize the secondary structure interaction via FORNA, available in [FORNA Webserver](#). The input for FORNA could be as following:

Still in FORNA, remove the "&" character in both sequences and secondary structure predictions. The result should be something like this:

Step 14: RNAHybrid interaction analysis

To verify interactions between a Target (such as lncRNAs) and a Query (such as miRNAs), an alternative program is RNAHybrid, which can be installed via Conda using the following command:

```
conda install bioconda::rnahybrid
```

To verify the interaction between a lncRNA (UCA1 in this example) and a miRNA (miR145 for example), you should run a command like this:

```
RNAhybrid -t ./Seqs/lncRNA/UCA1_001_corrected.fasta -m 3000 -q  
./Seqs/miRNA/miR_145.fasta -n 100 -b 100 -s 3utr_human > UCA1_interact_mir145.txt
```

The arguments used are the following:

-t → Target file path.

-m → Maximum target length to be used, should be at least equal to the target sequence max length.

-q → Query file path.

-n → Maximum query length to be used, should be at least equal to the query sequence max length.

-b → Maximum number of interactions to be predicted.

-s → specify the genome species.

The result should be a text file, with the following output:

```
mfe: -57.9 kcal/mol  
p-value: 0.253029  
position 770  
target 5' A CUU C CUCC AAU CC AG G CCA GG UCAUCC CUCAUCUCUUA A CUGCCGCCUAAAA A 3'  
GGCCAUG CUUC G AACA UUCCA GG AUCCC CAU CUU AGCA CU GUUCCU CUGGACC GAC AAGG  
UUGGUAC GGAG C UUGU AAGGU CC UAGGG GUA GAA UCGU GA UAAGGA GACCUUG GAC CUG UCC  
miRNA 3' U UU CAUA U A UUCC CCCUUU CACUC AC 5'
```

The interaction found on the paper is highlighted above.